

[勘誤 Erratum]

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Erratum: The Genus *Sympetrum* Newman, 1833 (Odonata: Libellulidae) in Taiwan: Distribution, Bionomics and a Report of a Newly Recorded Species

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Erratum: *Sympetrum baccha* (Selys, 1884) was described by Selys (1884) as *Diplax baccha* and subsequently transferred to the genus *Sympetrum*. Ma et al. (2022) summarized the current status of distribution, bionomics and reported a newly recorded species of *Sympetrum* in Taiwan. However, Ma et al. (2022) misspelled the scientific name of *Sympetrum baccha* (Selys, 1884) as *Sympetrum bacha* (Selys, 1884). The name “*Sympetrum bacha*” that appeared in all content of Ma et al. (2022) should be “*Sympetrum baccha*”. We thank Kai-Ti Lin (Department of Entomology, National Taiwan University, Taiwan), who brought the problem to our attention.

References

Ma, C.-H., Chen, S.-L., Lou, C.-M., Lee, I.-L. & Hu, F.-S. 2022. The genus *Sympetrum* Newman, 1833 (Odonata: Libellulidae) in Taiwan: Distribution, bionomics and a report of a newly recorded species. *Taiwanese Journal of Entomological Studies* 7 (3): 27–42. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7100644>

de Selys Longchamps, E. 1884. Révision des *Diplax* paléarctiques. *Annales de la Société Entomologique de Belgique* 28: 29–45.

勘誤：臺灣產赤蜻屬（蜻蜓目：蜻蜓科）：分布、生物學、新紀錄種報導

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勘誤：赤衣蜻蜓 (*Sympetrum baccha* (Selys, 1884)) 由 Selys (1884) 描述為 *Diplax baccha* 並隨後轉移至赤蜻屬 (*Sympetrum*)，Ma et al. (2022) 總結了臺灣產赤蜻屬的分布、生物學並報導一種新紀錄種，然而，Ma et al. (2022) 誤將赤衣蜻蜓的學名 “*Sympetrum baccha*” 誤用為 “*Sympetrum bacha*”，Ma et al. (2022) 內文中所有的 *Sympetrum bacha* 都應修正為 *Sympetrum baccha*。我們感謝林豈弟 (國立臺灣大學昆蟲學系) 注意到學名誤用的問題並告知本文作者。